

THE IMPORTANCE OF A CREATIVE APPROACH TO THE ORGANIZATION OF STUDENTS INDEPENDENT WORK AT UNIVERSITIES

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Annotation. The article offers a new understanding of the role, significance and share of students' independent work in the competency-based model of education, and argues for the need to revise approaches to understanding the tasks of independent work.

Key words: independent work, independence, independent education, practical, social, organizational, independent creative activity, technology, formation, competencies, ability to independently solve problems.

Аннотация. В статье предлагается новое понимание роли, значения и доли самостоятельной работы обучающихся в компетентностной модели образования, аргументируется необходимость пересмотра подходов к пониманию задач самостоятельной работы.

Ключевые слова: самостоятельная работа, самостоятельность, самостоятельное образование, практическая, социальная, организационная, самостоятельная творческая деятельность, технология, образование, компетенции, умение самостоятельно решать задачи.

Аннотация. Maqolada kompetensiyaga asoslangan ta'lim modelida talabalar mustaqil ishining o'rni, ahamiyati va ulushi haqida yangi tushuncha berilgan va mustaqil ish vazifalarini tushunishga yondashuvlarni qayta ko'rib chiqish zarurligi ta'kidlangan.

Калит сўзлар: mustaqil ishlash, mustaqillik, mustaqil bilim olish, amaliy, ijtimoiy, tashkiliy, mustaqil ijodiy faoliyat, texnologiya, shakllantirish, kompetentsiya, muammolarni mustaqil hal qila olish.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social transformations taking place in the modern world affect all spheres of society, including education, putting forward higher demands for the training and education of modern people. In these conditions, it is necessary that educational policy

contributes to the achievement of quality education and meets the current and future needs of the individual, society and the state.

In an increasingly competitive world market, it is important to further improving the efficiency of the personnel training system by developing the quality of education and scientific potential in ensuring the economic development of the country.

In modern Uzbekistan, higher education is one of the fastest growing areas. After all, a strong state with an innovative economy, a fair civil society where all human rights and interests are ensured, cannot be built without creating an impressive personnel reserve. Training qualified specialists with critical thinking and modern knowledge in the most in-demand professions is the primary task set by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev.

In Uzbekistan, there is a great understanding that constant investments in the so-called “human capital” and education are the key to the formation of a developed democratic state, a constant engine of progress and an indispensable condition for the modernization orientation of national development. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan rightly noted on this occasion, “the achievement of noble goals facing the people of Uzbekistan, the future of the country, its prosperity and well-being, what place it will take in the world community in the 21st century - all this depends, first of all, on the new generation, depends on how our children grow up.” This postulate has always received support and recognition at the state level, and moreover, it is becoming stronger every day in the minds of people, which creates a solid layer and basis for the bright and great future of Uzbekistan [1].

At the same time, radically improving the activities of higher educational institutions in the field of economics and finance, establishing an effective management system in them, introducing the latest pedagogical technologies into the educational process, organizing scientific activities based on world standards, further increasing their place in international rankings, and broadly attracting scientific- teaching staff with advanced foreign experience are the basis for training competitive personnel for the country’s economic and financial systems [2].

The problem of organizing independent activity of students in the learning process is one of the most pressing in modern pedagogy. A situation has arisen where established methods and forms of designing and implementing students’ independent work require reflection, correction, and new pedagogical solutions. Currently, the goals and objectives facing education are changing - the emphasis is shifting from “knowledge acquisition” to the formation of “competence”, and it is being reoriented towards a personality-oriented approach.

Independent work of students, in accordance with the requirements of regulatory educational documents, is a mandatory component of the educational process of a university, since the purpose of this form of educational work is manifested in consolidating and deepening previously acquired knowledge in classroom training sessions.

Independent work of students at a university consists of a set of educational tasks that ensure proper mastery of the university educational program in strict accordance with the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard. However, new educational conditions place demands on the educational self-organization of students at a higher level of complexity, which is due to the need to develop multifaceted general cultural and professional competencies among students in higher education [3].

Independent work of students at a university is multifunctional in its educational significance, but some of the important tasks are the following: development in students of the necessary educational independence and initiative, creative flexibility of thinking, abilities to self-organize, self-improvement and self-realization in the educational process. Therefore, turning to the analysis of the essence of students' independent work at a university requires considering it from the standpoint of creativity and the degree of independence of students in the learning process. In this context, the following types of independent work of university students are distinguished:

- independent work according to the model: low level of independence of students;
- independent work of a reconstructive-variable type: threshold level of educational independence of students;
- heuristic independent work: advanced level of educational independence of students;
- intra-subject and inter-subject independent research work: high level of educational independence of students. [4]

In the university education system, the need to develop an individual who not only has deep knowledge, skills and abilities in a certain professional field, but also is capable of self-realization and self-development in various fields of activity, and is able to creatively approach solving pressing life problems, is increasingly recognized. A modern university graduate is a person with a high level of independence and professional competence, capable of effective work in his specialty at the level of world standards, ready for constant professional growth [5].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical analysis of pedagogical literature shows that many researchers as N.G. Dairi, B.P. Esipov, G.E. Kovaleva, L.M. Pimenova, L.A. Ponomarev. They identify this feature as this basis personality, as independence.

Problems of student's independent work at university find their way coverage in scientific and methodological literature. These problems are studied by G.S. Zakirov, V.D. Zemzyulina, E.V. Zakharova, I. Kovalevsky. However, in this literature, unfortunately, the problems and features of student's independent work in the context of introducing into practice university life multi-level training system and student education.

The problem of independent work has worried the minds of many teachers for a number of centuries. Thus, the concept of "independent work" was reflected in the works of the classics of pedagogy: A. Disterweg, T. Campanella, Ya.A. Comenius, M. Montaigne, J.-J. Russo, I.G. Pestalozzi, K.D. Ushinsky and others. The modernization of education, which actively began in the pedagogy of Western Europe and the USA in the 19th century, placed special emphasis on the development of independence and initiative of students. Waldorf schools, the Mannheim education system, the Dalton plan system, teaching technologies using the project method, etc. corresponded to this principle.

S.I. Zinoviev notes that in higher education the concept of independence is associated with the idea of independence in choosing ways and means of solving the problems facing a person. This means that the student must carry out independent work without guidance and assistance from university teachers. But it should be noted that excessive independence can reduce the effectiveness of the result of a student's independent activity.

The problem of independence is reflected in the studies of V.P. Bespalko, L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontyeva, I.Ya. Lerner, S.L. Rubinshteina, G.I. Shchukina, I.S. Yakimanskaya and many other teachers and psychologists of our time. Analysis of pedagogical works in the field of independent activity revealed that currently the term "independent work" is revealed from different positions:

- teaching method (Yu.K. Babansky, I.Ya. Lerner, etc.);
- type of educational activity (I.Ya. Zimnyaya, L.D. Nikandrov, etc.);
- form of organization of training sessions (V.A. Slastenin, B.P. Esipov);
- teaching aid (A.N. Leontyev, P.I. Pidkasisty).

Independent educational work is usually understood as an active activity of students organized by a teacher, aimed at achieving a specific goal and carried out at a specially designated time. The result of independent work is the search for new

knowledge, its comprehension and analysis, consolidation, formation and development of practical skills, generalization and systematization of the experience gained. In the “Modern Dictionary of Pedagogy”, independent work is defined as “a method of teaching and self-education, a prerequisite for the didactic connection of various methods with each other”.

E.V. Shcherbakova considers the independent work of students as a pre-planned activity, “carried out according to the instructions and with the methodological guidance of the teacher, but without his direct participation”. Independent work is intended not only for mastering a specific discipline, but also for developing skills for independent work in general - in educational, scientific, and professional activities.

According to V.I. Zagvyazinsky, creativity begins precisely when the problem does not have a ready-made standard solution or when known solution methods do not produce results. In this case, knowledge is obtained using hypotheses, assumptions, guesses, intuition, and the result of the educational process is the discovery of something new.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research was based on the methodological concepts introduced by these researchers: N.G. Dairi, B.P. Esipov, G.E. Kovaleva, L.M. Pimenova, L.A. Ponomarev . The study presents descriptive statistics to establish certain evidence, namely the preferences of bachelor’s and master’s students regarding the preferred structure, type, and form of independent work. The practical goal of the work is to establish the percentage of students who prefer various types of independent work, and does not involve any more complex forms of statistical research. The results of this study will themselves be the basis for further research in this area.

IV. RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE

It is important for us to define independent work as a process of creative thinking of students when solving any problem, task, or mastering this or that material, regardless of whether this happens in the classroom or at home.

We include among the signs of independent work of students:

- allocation of special time (classroom or extracurricular) for independent work;
- the presence of a teacher’s assignment that requires certain mental or physical efforts of students;
- independent completion of tasks by students;
- availability of work results that reflect one’s own understanding of the problem [6].

Thus, in higher education didactics, independent work is considered, on the one hand, as a form of teaching and a type of educational activity carried out without the direct intervention of a teacher, and on the other hand, as a means of involving students in independent cognitive activity, a means of developing in them methods of organizing it.

The following can be considered important requirements for students' independent work:

- ensuring an optimal combination of volumes of independent work carried out both in the classroom (in contact with the teacher) and outside the classroom (completely independent work performed in a free mode);
- pedagogically and methodologically competent organization of all interrelated stages of students' independent work in various conditions;
- providing students with the necessary teaching materials for the most effective performance of independent work in order to transform this process into a process of creative activity;
- organization of control of independent work and measures to encourage students for its high-quality implementation [7].

V. DISCUSSIONS

The main task of organizing students' independent work is to develop students' readiness to manage their own cognitive activity in order to acquire individual knowledge. By performing any type of work independently, a student acquires the ability to take responsibility, independently solve problems that arise, and find constructive solutions.

Independent work of students is a multidimensional phenomenon that is considered from the perspective of several functions. The educational function promotes the systematization and consolidation of knowledge in certain disciplines, the developmental function promotes the development of attention, memory, thinking, speech, cognitive abilities, the educational function forms motivation for educational activities, self-organization and self-control. Performing various types of independent work contributes to the development of independence of the individual as a whole [8].

It is necessary to distinguish between the concept of "independent work" and the concept "self-education". Self-education is a system of constant updating of knowledge, and it goes beyond the scope of academic work at a university. However, its tasks are much broader than the tasks of independent work. Self-education, in contrast to independent work, is not only a form of mastering, deepening and acquiring new knowledge during study at a university, but also a form of continuing the education

of young specialists after graduation. Consequently, the concept of “independent work” and the concept of “self-education” have different meanings. Confusion of these concepts leads to confusion in the choice of means, forms and methods of their practical implementation.

In our opinion, independent work should be understood only as an integral part of self-education, pursuing broader goals. Some scientists consider independent work as a means of developing generalized skills, cognitive independence, creative activity and socialization of the individual, and associate it with the ability to self-organize.

In fact, independent work of students is planned by each teacher in the work program of the discipline, and its credit types are recorded in the technological map, in which students can always find information about the amount of independent work, the time of their completion and the maximum score when assessing the results of their implementation. The amount of time allocated for extracurricular independent work is reflected: in the curriculum as a whole for theoretical training, for each of the cycles of disciplines, for each discipline, in the work programs of academic disciplines with an approximate distribution by sections or specific topics.

The formation of data and other competencies cannot be fully realized if independent work of students is not emphasized. Students should recognize independent work as a freely chosen, internally motivated activity. The main components of independent work are motivation, definition and awareness of the goal, choice of individual ways of performing the activity, control, and criteria for assessing the performance of the activity. At the university, the main types of independent work of students are: preparation for lectures, seminars, tests, exams, completion of essays, coursework and projects, final qualifying work.

The modern pedagogical system involves the introduction of new ideas, technologies, forms and methods of its organization into the educational process with the aim of developing not only cognitive activity, but also its highest level - the creative activity of the individual in the cognitive process based on internal motives.

As known, one of the effective technologies leading to the improvement of students' creative activity in the process of performing independent work is problem-based learning as “a special type of learning, the characteristic feature of which is its developing function in relation to creative abilities.”

Problem-based learning involves creative assimilation of knowledge, and for its implementation it is necessary to have a certain problem or problematic situation, the solution of which will require students to intensively search for new knowledge and new ways of action. “Problem-based learning is an organization of training sessions

that involves the creation, under the guidance of a teacher, of problem situations and the active independent activity of students to resolve them, as a result of which the creative mastery of professional knowledge, skills and abilities and the development of thinking abilities occur.” [9].

Thus, one of the tasks of problem-based learning is the formation and development of creative thinking. The main way to successfully develop mental activity is to complete tasks and tasks not according to an algorithm, but in the process of independently searching for unknown new knowledge, which is what happens within the framework of solving problematic problems.

We build the system of independent work for students according to the principle of increasing its importance, volume, complexity and levels of implementation. The tasks offered to students for independent work include four levels: reproductive, reproductive-creative, creative, research. Tasks of the first and second levels require students’ ability to consciously perceive and understand information, apply well-known operating techniques, and perform tasks in accordance with the proposed model; at the same time, be able to transform existing knowledge in order to understand the sample, and then apply a known method of activity.

The tasks of the third and fourth levels are more complex and require in-depth preparation and integration of several types of activities. Students demonstrate mastery of new ways and techniques of action, creative application of knowledge in new situations, problem solving based on independent search, foresight, and forecasting. All tasks at these levels are aimed at developing general cultural and professional competencies and are fundamentally problematic in nature.

To sum up, the organization of independent work is carried out on the basis of individual capabilities, interests, motivation of students and involves a variety of forms and methods of activity, acquiring a variable character.

VI. CONCLUSION

In light of the new situation, the actualization of the problem of continuous education, reduction of classroom activities, transition from “listening” to lectures and increasing the share of independent work, the logical scheme “teacher-student” is radically changing. The student comes to the fore; he or she must take a leading position, and the teacher becomes his or her facilitator.

The relevance of the problem of students mastering the methods of independent cognitive activity is dictated by the fact that during the training period the foundations of professionalism are laid and the skills of independent professional activity are formed.

We know that modern society needs specialists who can quickly make non-standard decisions, act creatively, independently, who can contribute to the development of a particular industry. Independent activity is a form of educational and cognitive activity in which such qualities of a student's personality as organization, determination, creativity, and responsibility are manifested. Independent activity of students contributes to the formation of initiative, discipline, accuracy, and a sense of responsibility necessary for a future specialist in training and professional activities.

We came to conclusion that independent activity of students is considered as a purposeful, self-organized, self-managed activity, structured by the student himself, built on deep internal motives. In modern conditions, a student's ability to act independently takes on a qualitatively new meaning, which is determined by the university graduate's readiness to quickly adapt to practical professional activities in rapidly changing conditions. The fact that independent work of a student is the main way to foster independence and develop professional competence is no longer in doubt.

In addition, independent activity is work that is performed without the direct participation of the teacher, but according to his instructions, at a time specially provided for this, while students consciously strive to achieve their goals, using their efforts and expressing in one form or another the result of mental or physical actions.

It is through independent activity that a high culture of mental work is developed. In the process of such work, the individual abilities of students, their inclinations and interests are most fully revealed, which contribute to the development of the ability to analyze facts and phenomena, teach independent thinking, which leads to creative development and creation of one's own opinion, one's views, ideas, one's position [10].

Summarizing the above, we emphasize that the organization of independent work of students in the context of the implementation of the Program for Advanced Professional Training of Graduates of the New Generation is an important condition for their high-quality professional growth and the development of creative activity. No knowledge that is not supported by independent activity can become the true property of a person. Independent work forms independence not only as a set of skills and abilities, but also as a character trait that plays a significant role in the personality structure of a modern specialist of the highest category.

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